

Thiocyanate as Reagent for the Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium in Presence of *o*-Phenanthroline

S. P. ARYA

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-132 119

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Thiocyanate complexes of vanadium in different oxidation states have been used for the spectrophotometric determination of the element. Among these include the extractions of V^V -thiocyanate ternary complexes^{1,2}, V^{IV} -thiocyanate complexes³⁻⁵, and V^{II} -thiocyanate complex⁶ in presence of 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline into different organic solvents. V^{II} -thiocyanate complex⁷ in aqueous acetone has been proposed but has little to recommend in applied analysis. The extraction of V^{III} -thiocyanate complex^{8,9} is also reported which can be extracted into chloroform in presence of diantipyrylmethane¹⁰ but the method has not been used for the determination of the metal.

It has been observed that vanadium(V) gets reduced to vanadium(II) with mercury metal in the presence of thiocyanate in weakly acidic solutions and that the addition of *o*-phen to the greenish yellow V^{III} -thiocyanate extract gives an intense yellowish brown colour useful for spectrophotometric determination of vanadium.

Results and Discussion

For the reduction of vanadium(V) to vana-

dium(III) in acidic solutions, stannous chloride⁶, amalgams¹¹, hydrogen iodide¹², and electrolysis¹³ have been suggested. The last three take long time and need high acidity and only stannous chloride has been found to be convenient for analytical purpose. Dithionite¹⁴ has been used for the reduction of V^V to V^{III} but it can not be used at the acidity required for the formation of V^{III} -thiocyanate due to rapid decomposition and production of yellow colour and turbidity. At low acidities, mercury metal¹⁵ or thiocyanate⁶ reduces V^V to V^{IV} . It is found that in the presence of thiocyanate, mercury metal reduces V^V rapidly to V^{III} , giving greenish yellow V^{III} -thiocyanate complex.

The absorption maximum of yellow brown vanadium(III)-*o*-phen-thiocyanate complex in ethyl acetate is at 440 nm with a higher sensitivity than the simple vanadium(III) thiocyanate complex ($\lambda_{max}=395$ nm), while the reagent blank absorbs highly at less than 360 nm but little at 440 nm.

The vanadium(III)-thiocyanate complex is not extracted by chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and benzene. Under the optimum conditions,

tribenzylamine in chloroform, isoamyl acetate and isoamyl alcohol do not extract the complex well, even after longer shaking. *n*-Butanol and tributyl phosphate extract better but the best are methyl isobutyl ketone and ethyl acetate. Maximum extraction is achieved in 30 s, but the last two solvents required only 5 s, longer shaking decreasing the extraction (Table 1).

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF VIII-*o*-PHEN-SCN COMPLEX EXTRACTION WITH ETHYL ACETATE ON VARIOUS PARAMETERS

Acidity of extrn. ^a (M HCl)	0.1	0.4–0.6	1.0	2.0	4.0
Absorbance ^b	0.751	0.818	0.752	0.505	0.295
Concn. of <i>o</i> -phen (%, w/v) ^c (1 ml in 95% EtOH)	0	0.2	0.5	1.0–2.0	4.0
Max. absorbance ^b	0.325	0.646	0.818	0.838	0.820
Waiting time for max. absorbance (min)	—	17	10	5	0
KCNS(M) ^d	0.125	0.25	0.5	1.0	2.0 4–4.5
Absorbance ^b	0.438	0.636	0.752	0.818	0.830 0.860
Equilibration time (s) ^e	4–7	10	20	60	120 300
Absorbance ^b	0.920	0.900	0.838	0.770	0.718 0.532

(5 µg V ml⁻¹ in the aqueous phase)

^a3 M KCNS, 20 s equilibration time, 0.5% *o*-phen in EtOH, 10 min waiting time. ^bagainst ethyl acetate. ^c0.5 M HCl, 3 M KCNS 20 s equilibration time. ^d0.5 M HCl, 20 s equilibration time, 1% *o*-phen in EtOH, 5 min waiting time. ^e0.5 M HCl, 3 M KCNS, 1% *o*-phen in EtOH, 5 min waiting time.

The effect of adding different nitrogenous bases (pyridine, 1,2-dipyridyl and *o*-phenanthroline) to V^{III}-thiocyanate complex in ethylacetate was studied. All of them change the greenish yellow colour to yellowish brown, *o*-phen giving the highest absorbance at λ_{max} 440 nm. The solvent in which the nitrogenous base is dissolved also affects the absorbance. Acetone gives highest absorbance remaining stable for longest time among the solvents methanol, ethanol and acetone.

The effect of various parameters of the absorbance of the complex is shown in Table 1. The optimum conditions for the maximum absorbance of V^{III}-*o*-phen-thiocyanate complex are : reduction of V^V to V^{III} at 0.2 M HCl and 3 M thiocyanate with mercury metal and extraction of the complex at 0.4–0.6 M HCl and 4–4.5 M KCNS with ethyl acetate for 5 s, addition of 1 ml of *o*-phen solution (1.0–2.0% in acetone) to the ethyl acetate solution of V^{III}-thiocyanate complex, mixing and waiting for 5 min before measurement of absorbance.

As the complex is light-sensitive, the base should be added to the V^{III}-thiocyanate extract after wrapping up the flask with black paper and transferred to the cells just before measurement. Thus the complex is stable for more than 1 h and obeys Beer's law in the range 0.4–6.0 µg V ml⁻¹ solvent having sensitivity of 0.0045 µg V cm⁻².

Sulphate and chloride can be tolerated upto 1.0 g/20 ml. Acetate (500), ttrate (500), citrate (400), phosphate (400), sulphosalicylic acid (300), ascorbic acid (300) and EDTA (50) do not interfere (figure in parentheses indicates the amount of the anion present in mg). Oxalate, nitrate and fluoride should be absent. The influence of various cations which are tolerated to a varying degree (figure in parenthesis is in mg) : Zn^{II} (50); Be^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} (20 each); Sn^{II}, Sb^{III}, Mn^{II} (10 each); Ce^{IV}, Zr^{IV}, Th^{IV}, As^V, Co^{II}, U^{VI} (5 each); Pt^{IV}, Pd^{II} (2 each); Ni^{II} (1); Cr^{III} (0.5) present in 20 ml of aqueous phase are tolerated. Sodium tartrate (0.5 g) is added to prevent the hydrolytic precipitation in tin and antimony. On mixing with *o*-phen, cadmium thiocyanate gives a white precipitate in ethyl acetate which is filtered off, cobalt thiocyanate gives a brown precipitate settling to the bottom of the flask allowing decantation of the clear solution for measuring absorbance. In case of U and Pt, reduction with Hg is done for 3 min to get a colourless solution. Mo^{VI}, Fe^{III} and Cu^{II} are little tolerated.

The proposed method is quite sensitive and can be used for the determination of microgram amounts of vanadium in different samples. The method is simple, inexpensive, rapid and makes use of commonly available reagents. It compares favourably with other spectrophotometric methods as indicated by its comparison (Table 2) with some of the methods of vanadium determination.

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF THE PRESENT METHODS WITH OTHER METHODS OF V DETERMINATION

Reagent	Extractant (λ _{max})	Beer's law (µg ml ⁻¹)/(Sandell sensitivity, µg V cm ⁻²)	Interfering ions
VV, 3- <i>N</i> -salicyli- neamino-4-hydro- oxybenzene sulpho- nic acid ^a	— (420 nm)	0–4.0 (0.044)	Mo ^{VI} , Fe ^{III} Al ^{III} , Cu ^{II}
VV, <i>N</i> -allyl- <i>N'</i> - (<i>p</i> -benzoyl-gly- cine)thiourea ^b	Isoamyl alcohol (360 and 380 nm)	1–22 ppm (0.048)	W ^{VI} , Ti ^{IV} , Fe ^{III} , Hg ^{II} , Cu ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Co ^{II}
VIII-ferrone ^c	TBA/CHCl ₃ (430 nm)	0–5.0 (2.1 × 10 ⁻³)	Mo ^{VI} , Bi ^V , Ti ^{IV} , Zr ^{IV} , Sn ^{II}
VV, H ₂ O ₂ ^d	— (450–460 nm)	100 (0.18)	Mo ^{VI} , Cr ^{VI} , Ta ^V , Nb ^V , Ti ^{IV} , Ce ^{IV} , Fe ^{III} , Cu ^{II} , Ni ^{II}
Present method	Ethyl acetate (440 nm)	0.4–6.0 (0.0045)	Mo ^{VI} , Fe ^{III} Cu ^{II}

^aRef. 16. ^bRef. 17. ^cRef. 18. ^dRef. 7.

Experimental

A stock solution of vanadium (5 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared from sodium metavanadate and standardised by the oxine method¹². Suitable dilutions were made to get 100 or 10 µg V ml⁻¹. Solutions of other

NOTES

elements were prepared by dissolving their suitable salts in distilled water or dilute HCl. 10 M HCl (A.R.) and 8 M potassium thiocyanate (B.D.H.) were used. A 1% 1,10-phenanthroline (*o*-phen, E. Merck) solution in acetone was prepared.

Procedure: To a solution containing not more than 150 μg of vanadium in about 5 ml volume, were added the solutions of HCl (1 ml) and potassium thiocyanate (4 ml). The solution was shaken for 1 min with mercury (4 ml). The thiocyanate solution (6 ml) was then added and volume of the aqueous phase was made to 20 ml. The greenish yellow solution was extracted for 5 s with ethyl acetate or methyl isobutyl ketone (10 ml). The aqueous phase along with mercury was again extracted with the solvent (10 ml) for 5 s. To the combined extract, *o*-phen solution (1 ml) was added and the volume was made upto 25 ml. The flask was wrapped to prevent exposure of the solution to light. The contents were mixed thoroughly and after 5 min the absorbance of the complex was measured at 440 nm with a Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer, against a similarly prepared blank.

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